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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF SELF
EMULSIFYING DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM FOR BCS CLASS –
II DRUGS USING TRIMETHOPRIM AS A MODEL DRUG***** L. Ramanamma^{1*}, Suwendu Kumar Sahoo¹, Sharmila Dusi², D.S.V.S. Prasad²**¹Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Gitam Institute of Pharmacy,
Gitam University, Visakhapatnam, A.P, INDIA.²Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, College of Pharmaceutical, Andhra University,
Andhra University, Visakhapatnam, A.P, INDIA.**Abstract:**

Oral route is the easiest and most convenient route for drug administration. Oral drug delivery systems being the most cost-effective and leads the worldwide drug delivery market. The major problem in or it get solubility and then absorbed oral route is a problematic route for those drug molecules which exhibit poor aqueous solubility. When a drug is administered by oral route the first step for it to get solubilized and then absorbed. formulations is low and erratic bioavailability, which mainly results from poor aqueous solubility. This may lead to high inter- and intra subject variability, lack of dose proportionality and therapeutic failure. It is estimated that 40% of active substances are poorly water soluble (water insoluble in nature). For the improvement of bio-availability of drugs with such properties presents one of the greatest challenges in drug formulations. Various technological strategies are reported in the literature including solid dispersion cyclodextrins complex formation, or micronization, and different technologies of drug delivery systems. Including these approaches self-emulsifying drug delivery system (SEDDS) has gained more attention for enhancement of oral bio-availability with reduction in dose. SEDDS are isotropic mixtures of oil, surfactants, solvents and co-solvents/surfactants. The principal characteristic of these systems is their ability to form fine oil-in-water (o/w) emulsions or micro-emulsions upon mild agitation following dilution by an aqueous phase. For lipophilic drugs, which have dissolution rate-limited absorption, SEDDS may be a promising strategy to improve the rate and extent of oral absorption. This review article explains how self-emulsifying drug delivery systems can increase the solubility and bioavailability of poorly soluble drug.

Key words: Self emulsifying drug delivery system (SEDDS); oil, co-surfactant; surfactant; self-micro-emulsifying drug; delivery systems (SMEDDS).

Corresponding Author:*L. Ramanamma,**

Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences,

Gitam Institute of Pharmacy,

Gitam University, Visakhapatnam, A.P, INDIA.

E-mail: ramanivarahalu@gmail.com

Phone No: +91-9492144106

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Oral route is the easiest and most convenient route for non invasive administration. Oral drug delivery system is the most cost-effective and leads the worldwide drug delivery market. The oral route is a problematic route for those drug molecules which exhibit poor aqueous solubility. When a drug is administered by oral route the first step for it to get solubilized and then absorbed.

Approximately 40% of new chemical drug moieties have poor aqueous solubility and it is a major challenge to modern drug delivery system. The rate limiting step for the absorption of these types of drugs is their solubilization in the gastrointestinal tract. The drugs with poor aqueous solubility and high permeability are classified as class II drug by Biopharmaceutical classification system (BCS). Different approaches like micronization, solid dispersion, and complexation with cyclodextrins are used for formulation development, but in some selected cases, these approaches have been successful. [1]

Table – 1: Application of SEDDS in Relation to BCS classification. [2]

BCS Class	Aqueous Solubility	Membrane Permeability	Hurdles Overcome by SEDDS
I	High	High	Enzymatic degradation, Gut wall efflux
II	Low	High	Solubilization, Bio-availability
III	High	Low	Enzymatic degradation, Gut wall efflux, Bio-availability
IV	Low	Low	Solubilization, Enzymatic degradation, Gut wall efflux, Bio-availability

Self-emulsifying drug delivery systems (SEDDS) have gained exposure for their ability to increase solubility and bioavailability of poorly soluble drugs. SEDDSs are isotropic mixtures of oils and surfactants; sometimes it contains co-solvents, and it can be used for the design of formulations in order to improve the oral absorption of highly lipophilic compounds. SEDDSs emulsify spontaneously to produce fine oil-in-water emulsions when introduced into an aqueous phase under gentle agitation. SEDDS can be administered orally in soft or hard gelatine capsules and form fine, relatively stable oil-in-water emulsions upon aqueous dilution. [3]

Self-emulsifying formulations spread readily in the gastrointestinal tract (GIT), and the GI motility of the

stomach and the intestine provide the necessary agitation for self emulsification. These systems have the advantage that the drug in dissolved form and the small droplet size provides a large interfacial area for the drug absorption.[4] SEDDSs typically produce emulsions with a droplet size between 100–300 nm while self-micro-emulsifying drug delivery systems (SMEDDSs) form transparent micro-emulsions with a droplet size of less than 50 nm. SEDDSs are physically stable formulations that are easy to manufacture, but when compared with emulsions, which are sensitive and meta-stable dispersed forms. Thus, for lipophilic drug compounds that exhibit dissolution rate-limited absorption, these systems may offer an improvement in the rate and extent of absorption and result in more reproducible blood-time profiles. [5] The term self emulsification generally referred as the formation of small droplets when two immiscible liquids come in contact with each other due to reduction of interfacial tension between those two phasee . [6]

Composition of SEDDSs

The self-emulsifying process depends on. [7]

- The nature of the oil and surfactant
- The concentration of surfactant
- The temperature at which self-emulsification occurs

Oils: Oils are the most important excipient because oils can solubilize the lipophilic drug in a specific amount and it can facilitate self-emulsification and increase the fraction of lipophilic drug transported via the intestinal lymphatic system, thereby increasing absorption from the GI tract. [8] Both long-chain triglyceride and medium-chain triglyceride oils with different degrees of saturation have been used for the formulation of SEDDSs. Modified or hydrolyzed vegetable or edible oils have contributed widely to the success of SEDDSs owing to their formulation and physiological advantages. [7] Novel semi synthetic medium-chain triglyceride oils have surfactant properties and are widely replacing the regular medium-chain triglyceride. [8]

Surfactant: Non-ionic surfactants with high hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB) values are used in formulation of SEDDSs (e.g., Tween, Labrasol, Labrafac CM 10, Cremophore, etc.). Emulsifiers derived from natural sources are expected to be safer the synthetic once. The usual surfactant strength ranges between 30–60% w/w of the formulation in order to form a stable SEDDS. A large quantity of surfactant may irritate the GIT and it can be proved that the Non-ionic surfactants are to be less toxic as compared to ionic surfactants. Surfactants have a

high HLB and hydrophilicity, which assists the immediate formation of o/w droplets and/or rapid spreading of the formulation in the aqueous media. Surfactants are amphiphilic in nature and they can dissolve or solubilize relatively high amounts of hydrophobic drug compounds. This can prevent precipitation of the drug for prolonged existence of drug molecule within the GI lumen.[9]

Cosolvents: Co-solvents like ethanol, propylene glycol, polyethylene glycol, polyoxyethylene, propylene carbonate, tetrahydrofurfuryl alcohol polyethylene glycol ether (Glycofurol), etc., may help to dissolve large amounts of hydrophilic surfactants or the hydrophobic drug in the lipid base. These solvents sometimes play the role as co-surfactant in the microemulsion systems.[10] Although alcohol free self-emulsifying micro emulsions have also been described in the literature.

Why SEDDS are needed?

SEDDS are promising approach for oral delivery of poorly water-soluble compounds. It can be achieved by pre-dissolving the compound in a suitable solvent and fill the formulation into capsules. The oral drug delivery of hydrophobic drugs can be made possible by SEDDS. The main benefit of this approach is that pre-dissolving the compound overcomes the initial rate limiting step of particulate dissolution in the aqueous environment within the GI tract. However, a potential problem is that the drug may precipitate out of solution when the formulation disperses in the GI tract, particularly if a hydrophilic solvent is used (e.g. polyethylene glycol). If the drug can be dissolved in a lipid vehicle there is less potential for precipitation on dilution in the GI tract, as partitioning kinetics will favor the drug remaining in the lipid droplet.[11]

Table – 2: Example of surfactants, co-surfactant, and co-solvent used in commercial formulations. [12]

Excipient Name (commercial name)
<u>Surfactants/co-surfactants</u>
Polysorbate 20 (Tween 20) Polysorbate 80 (Tween 80) Sorbitan mono-oleate (Span 80) Polyoxy-40- hydrogenated castor oil (Cremophor RH40) Polyoxy ethylated glycerides (Labrafil M 2125 Cs) Polyoxy ethlated oleic glycerides (Labrafil M1944 Cs)
<u>Co-solvents</u>
Ethanol Glycerin Polypylene glycol. Polyethylene glycol.
<u>Lipid ingredients</u>
Corn oil mono ,di ,,tri-glycerides DL-alpha-Tocopherol Fractionated triglyceride of palm seed oil (medium-chain triglyceride) Medium chain mono-and di-glycerides Corn oil Olive oil Oleic acid Sesame oil Soyabean oil Peanut oil Beeswax Hydrogenated soyabean oil Hydrogenated vegetable oils

Potential Advantages of these Systems Include.[12]

- Protection of sensitive drug substances
- More consistent drug absorption,
- Selective targeting of drug(s) toward specific absorption window in GIT,
- Protection of drug(s) from the gut environment.
- Control of delivery profiles
- Reduced variability including food effects
- Enhanced oral bioavailability enabling reduction in dose
- High drug loading efficiency
- For both liquid and solid dosage forms.

Drawback of SEDDS: [13-15]

- The main drawback for the development of self emulsifying drug delivery systems (SEDDS) and other lipid-based formulations is the lack of good *in vitro* models for assessment of the formulations for SEDDS .The traditional dissolution methods does not work, because these formulations potentially are dependent on digestion prior to release of the drug. To mimic this, an *in vitro* model simulating the digestive processes of the duodenum has been developed. This *in vitro* model needs further development and validation is carried out before its strength can be evaluated. Further development will be carried out on the basis of *in vitro* - *in vivo* correlations and therefore different prototype lipid based formulations needs to be developed and tested *in vivo* in a suitable animal model. Future studies will address the development of the *in vitro* model
- Chemical instabilities of drugs.

- Large quantities of surfactants (30 – 60%) irritate the gastrointestinal tract.
- Volatile co-solvents in the conventional self-emulsifying formulations migrate into the shells of soft or hard gelatin capsules.
- Lack of good prognostic *in vitro* models for assessment of the formulations is a great obstacle.
- Ordinary *in-vitro* dissolution method does not work because these formulations depend on digestion prior to release of the drug.
- The precipitation tendency of the drug on dilution may be higher due to the dilution effect of the hydrophilic solvent.
- It is disputing to validate the formulations with several components.
- Further development of formulation is based only on *in vitro* – *in vivo* correlations.

Properties of SEDDS

- They are able to self emulsify rapidly in gastro-intestinal fluids & under the influence of gentle agitation provided by Peristaltic and other movements of gastro intestinal tract, they form a fine o/w emulsion. [16,17]
- They can effectively incorporate drug (hydrophobic or hydrophilic) within the oil surfactant mixture.
- They can be used for liquid as well as solid dosage forms.
- They require lower dose of drug with respect to conventional dosage forms.

TYPES OF SEDDS

On the basis of the water solubility of components, SEDDS can be classified as shown in Figure – 1.

Figure – 1: Lipid formulation classification system (LFCS)**a) Non-water soluble component systems**

These systems are isotropic mixtures of lipids & lipophilic surfactants having HLB value less than 12 that self emulsify to form fine oil in water emulsion in aqueous medium. Self emulsification is generally obtained at a surfactant level above 25% w/w. But at a surfactant level of 50-60% w/w the emulsification process may be compromised by formation of viscous liquid crystalline gels at the oil/water interface. This system is also known as Type-II SEDDS according to lipid formulation classification System (LFCS). [18]

Poorly water soluble drugs can be incorporated in SEDDS & encapsulated in capsules (hard or soft gelatin) to produce convenient single unit dosage forms.

These systems offer advantages -

- They are able to generate large interfacial areas which cause efficient partitioning of drug between oil droplets and the aqueous phase.
- They can overcome the slow dissolution step typically observed with solid dosage forms.

b) Water soluble component system

These systems are formulated by using hydrophilic surfactants with HLB more than 12 and cosolvents such as Ethanol, Propylene Glycol & Polyethylene glycols. Type III SEDDS are commonly known as self micro-emulsifying drug delivery systems (SMEDDS).[19]

Type III formulations can be further divided into type III A & Type III B formulations in order to identify more hydrophilic forms. In Type IIIB, the content of hydrophilic surfactants and cosolvents is increased and lipid content is reduced.

The distinction between SEDDS & SMEDDS formulation is commonly based on particle size and optical clarity of resultant dispersion. Thus SEDDS formulations typically provide opaque dispersions with particle size greater than 100 nm while SMEDDS disperse to give small droplets with particle size less than 100 nm and provide optically clear or slightly opalescent dispersions.

SEDDS and SMEDDS have played an important role in the improvement of solubility as well as bioavailability of drugs with poor aqueous solubility. An example of the marketed SMEDDS formulation is Neoral Cyclosporine formulation in which corn oil, derived mono, di and triglycerides were used as lipid phase, cremophor RH 40 as surfactant, propylene glycol & ethanol as cosolvent along with α -tocopherol as an antioxidant.[2] Neoral spontaneously forms a transparent & thermodynamically stable dispersion with droplet size below 100 nm when introduced into an aqueous medium.[20,21]

SEDDS may be solid or liquid in nature and they may be formulated into tablets, capsules, pellets, solid dispersions, microspheres, nanoparticles or dry emulsions.

➤ **Solid Self Emulsifying Drug Delivery System (s- SEDDS):**

As SEDDS may exist in liquid or solid dosage form, but due to better stability as well as ease in handling and transportation, solid SEDDS are generally preferred over liquid SEDDS. Conventional solid SEDDS are capsules, solid dispersions and dry emulsions but recently, a number of other solid SEDDS have been prepared such as Pellets, Microspheres, Tablets, Beads, Implants & Suppositories.

Figure – 2: Types of Solid SEDDS

a) Self Emulsifying Capsules

Capsule having conventional liquid self emulsifying formulation, upon administration form droplets of micro emulsion spontaneously & then disperse in gastro intestinal tract and yield improved absorption. They however have certain limitations as if irreversible phase separation of microemulsion takes place, then drug absorption decreases. In such cases, to improve the absorption, sodium dodecyl sulphate is added to SE formulations & super-saturable SEDDS is formulated by using a small quantity of polymer in the formulation to prevent drug precipitation by generating & maintaining supersaturated state *in vivo*. These formulations contain a reduced amount of surfactant & minimize any gastrointestinal side effects. In the gastrointestinal tract, capsules disperse to form SES uniformly dispersed to form very fine droplets (in microns) & enhances bioavailability. Another type of SE capsules is solid SES filled into capsule.[22,23]

b) Dry Emulsion

It is mainly oil in water emulsion, converted into solid by using various techniques such as spray drying, using solid carrier adsorption or freeze drying technique.[24-26] Dry emulsion may be re dispersed in water before use. These are actually powders in which emulsification spontaneously occurs *in vivo* or after exposure to an aqueous solution. Dry emulsion technology not only avoids the use of harmful or toxic organic solvents but effectively removes the stability problems (such as phase separation, creaming & contamination by micro- organism during storage) associated with classic emulsion. MCT (Medium Chain Triglycerides) are generally used as oil phase for these formulations. Dry emulsions can be used for further preparation of tablets & capsules. This technique has been applied for poorly water soluble drug amlodipine. [27]

A new interesting development in this field is newly developed enteric coated dry emulsion formulations which are more appropriate for peptide & protein drugs oral delivery. These formulations are prepared by using surfactant, vegetable oil & pH responsive polymer followed by lyophilization. [28]

c) SE Solid Dispersion

Solid dispersions had widely being used to increase the dissolution rate and bioavailability of poorly water soluble drugs although stability is a major concern during their manufacturing. *Serajuddin* (1999) reported that these problems can be overcome by using self emulsifying excipients such as Gelucire 44/14, Gelucire 50/02, Labrasol, Transcutol and

TPGS. [29-31]

Hot-melt granulation is a widely used technique for the preparation of solid dispersion. *Gupta et al.*, prepared SE solid dispersion granules of seven drugs using this technique including four carboxylic acid containing drugs, an amide containing drug (Phenacetin), a hydroxyl containing drug & a drug having no proton donating groups (Progesterone) in which Neusilin US2 was used as surface adsorbent and gelucire 50/13 was used as dispersion carrier.[32]

d) Self Emulsifying Tablets

First self emulsifying (SE) tablet of ubiquinone was prepared by *S. Nazzal et al.*, for studying effect of formulation ingredients on the release rate of drug & to evaluate an optimized self nano-emulsifying tablet formulation. Prepared nano-emulsion was adsorbed on granular materials and then compressed to form tablets. The dissolution profile of optimized self emulsifying tablet showed 80-90% drug release in 45 minutes.[33] Another drug Diclofenac has also been formulated as Self emulsifying tablet using goat fat and Tween 65.[34]

e) Self Emulsifying Implants

The drug carmustine (BCNU) is a chemotherapeutic agent used to treat malignant brain tumours but has short biological half life. Self emulsifying implant was prepared by using tributyrin, cremophor RH 40 & Labrafil 1944 in order to increase the stability of drug and compared its release from PLGA (Poly d, l – lactide co-glycolide) water implants, fabricated into wafers with a flat & smooth surface by compression moulding. It was observed that the *in vitro* half life of BCNU increased upto 130 minutes as compared to 45 minutes with intact BCNU.[35] Such wafers had higher *in vitro* anti tumour activity & were less susceptible to hydrolysis than wafers without SES.

Loomis et al. patented another type of co-polymers for implantable prostheses. These co-polymers were having hydrophilic region, bioresorbable region & at least two cross-linkable functional groups in a single polymer chain. Such copolymers have properties of self emulsification without requiring any emulsifier and can be used as good sealants for implantable prostheses. [36]

f) Self Emulsifying Suppositories

Some investigators have observed that solid SEDDS can not only increase GI adsorption but can also be used to enhance rectal and vaginal absorption. Glycyrrhizin given by oral route does not achieve therapeutic plasma concentration but satisfactory therapeutic levels can be achieved by the use of either

rectal or vaginal SE suppositories for the treatment of chronic hepatitis. Indomethacin suppositories have also been prepared by using self emulsifying technique. [37]

g) Self Emulsifying Beads

In SE systems, solid dosage forms can be developed by using less amount of excipient i.e. by formation of Beads. *Paradkar & Patil* used solvent evaporation technique for deposition of SE system into micro porous polystyrene beads. Porous polystyrene beads are having complex internal void structures. These beads are produced by copolymerization of monomers styrene and divinyl benzene. It is chemically inert, biocompatible and stable over a wide range of pH, temperature & humidity. Geometrical features of porous materials like bead size & pore architecture governs the loading efficiency and *in vitro* drug release from SES loaded porous poly styrene beads. [38]

h) Self Emulsifying Nanoparticles

Self emulsifying nanoparticles can be prepared by using various techniques. One of the techniques is solvent injection method in which molten lipid mass containing lipid, surfactant & drug is injected drop wise into a non-solvent system. Larger particles are removed by filtration and then filtrate is dried to get nanoparticles. By this method, self emulsifying nanoparticles using biodegradable homolipid with particle size of approximately 100nm are obtained with loading efficiency of 70-75%. [39]

Another technique is sonication emulsion-diffusion-evaporation which allows the loading of both 5-Flourouracil (5-FU) and antisense Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor (EGFR) plasmid in biodegradable PLGA/o-CMC nanoparticles. This combination i.e. PLGA & o-carboxymethyl chitosan shows self emulsifying effect without any surfactant stabilizer. [40] It was found that the release rate of 5-FU from self emulsifying nanoparticles was sustained for as long as three weeks.

Trickler et al used multiple emulsion (o/w/o) solvent evaporation method for preparation of self emulsifying nanoparticle system with chitosan and glyceryl monooleate (GMO) for the delivery of paclitaxel. These nanoparticles possessed bioadhesive properties & increased cellular association of the drug. [41]

i) Sustained Released Solid Self Emulsifying Drug Delivery System

(1) Self Emulsifying Microspheres: *You et al.* formulated solid SE sustained release microspheres using Zedoary Turmeric oil (ZTO), a traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), as oily phase. ZTO has potent pharmacological actions

such as tumour suppression, antibacterial & antithrombotic activity.

Quasi emulsion solvent diffusion method involving spherical crystallization was used for the preparation. The plasma concentration obtained after oral administration to rabbits showed the BA of 135.6% compared with conventional SEDDS i.e. liquid SEDDS. [42]

(2) Self Emulsifying Sustained Release Tablets: A gelled SEDDS has been developed by *Patil et al.* using colloidal silicon dioxide as gelling agent in order to minimize the amount of solidifying excipients required for conversion of liquid SEDDS into solid SEDDS. Colloidal SiO₂ reduces the amount of required solidifying excipients & aids in sustaining release rate of drug. [43]

Self Emulsifying (SE) tablet increase the penetration capacity of indomethacin through GI tract mucosal membrane. SE tablets were prepared by using glycerol monolaurate & tyloxapol (a copolymer of alkyl phenol & formaldehyde). [44]

A recent advance development in SE tablets is SE osmotic pump tablet of carvedilol. In this tablet, osmotic pump system [45] is chosen as a carrier for SE system and is able to provide excellent features like stable plasma concentration, a controllable drug release rate and bioavailability of 156.8% relative to conventional carvedilol tablets.

(3) Self Emulsifying Controlled Release Pellets: Pellets are the multiple unit dosage forms which possess a number of advantages over conventional solid dosage forms like ease of manufacturing, reduce the intra & inter subject variability of plasma profiles and also reduce GI irritation without lowering drug bioavailability. [46] SE controlled release pellets were prepared using extrusion/ spheronization by *Serratori et al.* by incorporating drugs into SES for enhancing the release rate of drug and coating the pellets with a water insoluble polymer to control the release rate.

It revealed that a combination of coating & self emulsification could effectively control *in vitro* release of drug and a range of release rates can be obtained. [47] In another study glyceryl palmito-stearate (Gelucire 54/02) & glyceryl behenate (Gelucire 70/02) were used for preparation of matrix sustained release pellets. [48]

➤ Based on size of droplets

1. Self emulsifying drug delivery system (SEDDS)

2. Self-micro-emulsifying drug delivery systems (SMEDDS)
3. Self-nanoemulsifying drug delivery systems (SNEDDS)

1. Self-nanoemulsifying drug delivery systems (SNEDDS)

Among the various approaches in improving solubility, SNEDDS appears to surpass the rest as SNEDDS requires simple and cost-effective manufacturing facilities. This is because SNEDDS is a physically stable lipid solution and it omits the need of high energy emulsification process. Also, SNEDDS appears to reduce the effect of food on bioavailability [49] and improve the onset of action. [50] Besides, many lipophilic compounds have been used as model drugs in SNEDDS formulations and the results are remarkable.

SNEDDS is composed of an isotropic mixture of oil, surfactant, co-surfactant and drug. [51] Upon ingestion, the isotropic mixture will come in contact with the aqueous phase of gastrointestinal tracts and form an oil-in-water nanoemulsion with the aid of gastrointestinal motility. This nanoemulsion can provide a large interfacial area for partitioning of drug between oil and aqueous phase and subsequently offer better dissolution rate.

2. Self-micro-emulsifying drug delivery systems (SMEDDS)

Poor bioavailability is a trouble, frequently faced in the drug development process. Enhancement of bioavailability of poorly water soluble drugs becomes farthest challenge for pharmaceutical scientist. Most of new drug candidates reveal low solubility in water, which leads to poor oral bioavailability, high intra- and inter-subject variability and lack of dose proportionality. Various approaches should use to improve the dissolution rate of the drug. Among them, Self micro emulsifying drug delivery systems (SMEDDS) have shown great pledge for enhancing bioavailability of poorly soluble compounds. Conventional SMEDDS are usually prepared in a liquid dosage form that can be administered in soft gelatin capsules, which have some disadvantages particularly in the manufacturing process and incompatibility problems with the shells of soft gelatin. Solid SMEDDS have recently been described and they surmount the disadvantages of liquid SMEDDS as well as exhibited more commercial potential and patient acceptability (Akhter *et al.*, 2012; Bhagwat *et al.*, 2012; Agarwal *et al.*, 2009). Many techniques are offered to convert conventional liquid SMEDDS to solid such as adsorptions to solid carriers, spray drying, spray cooling, melt extrusion, nanoparticles technology, supercritical fluid based

methods, etc. But among these the adsorption technique is simple and just involves addition of liquid formulation onto carriers by mixing in a blender. The resulting powder may then be filled directly into capsules or, alternatively, mixed with suitable excipients before compression into tablets. A significant benefit of the adsorption technique is good content uniformity. The SMEDDS can be adsorbed at high levels up to 70% w/w on to suitable carrier (Katteboina *et al.*, 2009).

MECHANISM OF SELF-EMULSIFICATION:

The process by which self-emulsification takes place is not yet well understood. However, according to Reiss, self-emulsification occurs when the entropy change that favors dispersion is greater than the energy required to increase the surface area of the dispersion.

In addition, the free energy of a conventional emulsion formation is a direct function of the energy required to create a new surface between the two phases and can be described by equation.

$$\Delta G = \sum_i N_i \pi r_i^2 \sigma$$

Where, G is the free energy associated with the process (ignoring the free energy of mixing), N is the number of droplets of radius r , and s represents the interfacial energy. With time, the two phases of the emulsion will tend to separate, in order to reduce the interfacial area, and subsequently, the free energy of the systems.[52]

Therefore, the emulsions resulting from aqueous dilution are stabilized by conventional emulsifying agents, which form a monolayer around the emulsion droplets, and hence, reduce the interfacial energy, as well as providing a barrier to coalescence.

Emulsification requiring very little input energy involves destabilization through contraction of local interfacial regions. For emulsification to occur, it is necessary for the interfacial structure to have no resistance to surface shearing.46 In the case of self emulsifying systems, the free energy required to form the emulsion is either very low and positive, or negative (then, the emulsification process occurs spontaneously).

FORMULATION OF SEDDS [53, 54]:

There are many different combinations that could be formulated for encapsulation in hard or soft gelatin which disperse to give fine colloidal emulsions. [55] The following points should be considered in the formulation of a SEDDS,

1. The solubility of the drug in different oil, surfactants and co-solvents.
2. The selection of oil, surfactant and co-solvent

based on the solubility of the drug and the preparation of the phase diagram. [56]

3. The preparation of SEDDS formulation by dissolving the drug in a mix of oil, surfactant and co-solvent.
4. The rate of digestion.
5. The solubilization capacity of the digested formulation.
6. The temperature at which self-emulsification occurs.

The addition of a drug to a SEDDS is critical because the drug interferes with the self emulsification process to a certain extent, which leads to a change in the optimal oil–surfactant ratio. So, the design of an optimal SEDDS requires preformulation solubility and phase-diagram studies. In the case of prolonged SEDDS, formulation is made by adding the polymer or gelling agent. [57]

TYPES OF FORMULATIONS

Single component lipid solutions: This is the simplest formulation that consists of the drug solubilized in a single excipient in plant oil or glyceride or a PEG. The evident advantage of this formulation approach is its congeneric simplicity. This formulation depend solvent on the gastrointestinal lipid handling pathways to promote emulsification which is essential for facile drug release and absorption with the exclusion of PEGs. In patients for whom lipid digestion has been determined by age or disease, the drug absorption is lower than the optimal. The single component PEG solutions often have high solubilizing power for poorly water soluble drugs. So, the degree of bioavailability enhancement is dose dependent, which renders PEG solution formulations poorly effective for high dose drugs. [58]

Self emulsifying formulations: Self emulsifying drug delivery systems are physically stable isotropic mixtures of oil, surfactant, co surfactant and solubilized drug substance that are suitable for oral delivery in soft and hard gelatin capsules. Depending on the excipient selection and relative composition of the formulation, aqueous dilution will result in

spontaneous formation of lipid droplets ranging in size from approximately 100 nm (SEDDS) to less than 50 nm (SMEDDS). The optimum concentrations or concentration ranges of oil, surfactant and co surfactant are necessary to promote self emulsification. Since droplet surface area is inversely proportional to diameter, smaller lipid droplets with their associated, greater surface area are thought to facilitate digestion, resulting in more lipid and uniform drug release and absorption. The improved drug absorption provided by self emulsifying for utilization is contingent upon the maintenance of the drug in the solubilized state until it can be absorbed from the GIT. In some instances, SMEDDS formulations have proven useful in palliating the enhancing effect that food can have on the absorption of poorly water-soluble drugs. [59]

Self emulsifying solid dispersion formulations [58]: Liquid self emulsifying formulations rely on micelle or solvent to fully solubilize the drug dose, which helps to ensure optimal absorption. However, the utility of these formulations can be limited by their inability to solubilize the entire drug dose in the volume of a single oral capsule. In these instances solid dispersion formulations, which may not fully solubilize the drug in the excipient matrix, can provide a viable, alternative oral formulation. These formulations consist of a dispersion of the drug in an inert excipient matrix, where the drug could exist in either the finely divided crystalline, solubilized or amorphous states or a mixture thereof. This can increase the dissolution rate of the drug and subsequent absorption from, the GI tract relative to the stable crystalline drug substance. These excipient have the potential to further increase the absorption of poorly water soluble drugs relative to previously used PEG solid dispersions and may also be filled directly into hard gelatin capsules in the molten state, thus obviating the former requirement for milling and blending prior to filling.

Observation of (from left to right) transparent; translucent with bluish tone; and milky turbid emulsions

Figure – 3: Physical appearance of different types of emulsions

NATURE AND DOSE OF THE DRUG

Drugs which are administered at very high dose are not suitable for SEDDS unless they have extremely good solubility in at least one of the components of SEDDS, preferably lipophilic phase. The drugs which have limited or less solubility in water and lipids are most difficult to deliver by SEDDS. The ability of SEDDS to maintain the drug in solubilised form is greatly influenced by the solubility of the drug in oil phase. As mentioned above if surfactant or co-surfactant is contributing to the greater extent in drug solubilisation then there could be a risk of precipitation, as dilution of SEDDS will lead to lowering of solvent capacity of the surfactant or co-surfactant. Equilibrium solubility measurements can be carried out to anticipate potential cases of

precipitation in the gut. However, crystallisation could be slow in the solubilising and colloidal stabilizing environment of the gut. Pouton's study reveal that such formulations can take up to five days to reach equilibrium and that the drug can remain in a super-saturated state for up to 24 hours after the initial emulsification event. It could thus be argued that such products are not likely to cause precipitation of the drug in the gut before the drug is absorbed, and indeed that super-saturation could actually enhance absorption by increasing the thermodynamic activity of the drug. There is a clear need for practical methods to predict the fate of drugs after the dispersion of lipid systems in the gastrointestinal tract.

Table – 3: Drug profile of Trimethoprim

1.	Chemical formula	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃
2.	IUPAC Name	5-[(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)methyl]pyrimidine-2,4-diamine
3.	Structure	
4.	Average weight	290.3177
5.	Water Solubility	0.58 mg/L (25 °C)
6.	pKa	7.16
7.	Log P	1.26
8.	Melting point	238-240 °C
9.	Refractivity	81.51
10	Pharmacokinetics:	
	Absorption	Approximately 45% of an oral dose is absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract
	Protein binding	42-46%
	Metabolism	Hepatic metabolism to oxide and hydroxylated metabolites.
	Excretion	Excreted unchanged in the urine
	Half Life	8 to 11hrs in adults with normal renal function

Pharmacodynamics:

Trimethoprim is a pyrimidine analogue that disrupts folate synthesis, an essential part of the thymidine synthesis path way .inhibition of the enzyme starves the bacteria of nucleotides necessary for DNA replication. The drug, therefore, exhibits bacterial activity.

Mechanism of action

Trimethoprim binds to dihydrofolate reductase and inhibits the reduction of hydrofolic acid (DHF) to tetrahydrofolic acid (THF). THF is an essential precursor in the thymidine synthesis pathway and interference with this path way inhibits bacterial

DNA synthesis. Trimethoprim's affinity for bacterial dihydrofolate reductase is several thousand times greater than its affinity for human dihydrofolate reductase.

Sulfamethoxazole inhibits dihydrofolate synthetase (akadihydroproate synthetase), an enzyme involved further upstream in the same pathway. Trimethaprim and sulfamethoxazole are commonly used in the combination due to their synergistic effects. This drug combination also reduces the development of resistance that is seen when either drug is used alone.

Categories: Anti-infectives, Anti-malarials, Folic acid antagonists, Anti-infective agents.

EXCIPIENT PROFILE**OLEIC ACID[79]****Table – 4:** Profile of oleic acid

S. No.	Property	Description
1.	Chemical formula	C18H34O2
2.	Chemical name	(9Z)-octa dec-9-enoic acid
3.	Synonyms	(9Z)-octa decenoic acid, (Z)-octadec-9-enoic acid, Cis-9-octa decenoic acid, Cis- Δ^9 -octadecenoic acid, Oleic acid
4.	Structure	
5.	Molecular Weight	282.4614
6.	Density	0.895 g/mL
7.	Boiling point	360 °C
8.	Appearance	Pale yellow or Brownish yellow oily liquid with lard-like odor
9.	Description	Oleic acid is a fatty acid that occurs naturally in various animal and vegetable fats and oils. It is odourless, colourless oil, although commercial samples may be yellowish. I chemical terms, oleic acid is classified as a mono-unsaturated Omega-9Fatty acid, abbreviated with a lipid number of 18:1 cis-9.
10.	Solubility	Water insoluble in nature
11.	Category	Emulsifying agent, emollient
12.	Storage	Store in a cool and dry place
13.	Stability	Stable and combustible. Incompatible with strong oxidizing agents

POLYETHYLENE GLYCOL-400[80]**Table – 5:** Profile of Polyethylene glycol-400

S No.	Property	Description
1.	Molecular formula	$C_{2n}H_{4n+2}O_{n+1}$, $n=8.2-9.1$
2.	Molar mass	380-420 g/mol
3.	Chemical structure	
4.	Density	1.128 g/cm ³
5.	Melting point	4-8 °C
6.	Viscosity	90.0 centistokes at 25 °C, 7.3 centistokes t at 99 °C
7.	Solubility	Water, acetone, Alcohols, Benzene, glycerine, glycols and aromatic hydro carbons.
8.	Description	PEG-400 (Polyethylene glycol-400) is a low molecular weight grade of polyethelene glycol. It is a clear colourless, viscous liquid.
9.	Functional Category	Surfactant

TWEEN 80[81]**Table – 6:** Profile of Tween80

S. No.	Property	Description
1.	Molecular formula	C ₆₄ H ₁₂₄ O ₂₆
2.	IUPAC Name	Polyoxyethelene (20) sorbitan monooleate
3.	Synonyms	AlkestTW80, Tween 80.
4.	Chemical structure	
5.	Molar Mass	1310 g/mol
6.	Appearance	Amber coloured viscous liquid
7.	Density	1.06-1.09 g/mL, oily liquid
8.	Boiling point	>100 °C
9.	Solubility	Very soluble in water. Soluble in ethanol, cotton seed oil, corn oil, ethyl acetate, methanol, toluene.
10.	Viscosity	300-500 centistokes (25 °C)
11.	Description	Polysorbate-80 is a viscous, water soluble yellow liquid. The hydrophilic groups in this compound are poly ethers are also known as polyoxyethelene groups which are polymers of ethylene oxide.
12.	Category	Co-surfactant

MATERIALS:**Table – 7:** List of materials

S. No.	Materials	Manufacturer
1.	Trimethoprim	Central Drug House (P) Ltd.
2.	Oleic acid	LOBAL Chemie
3.	PEG-400	LOBAL Chemie
4.	Tween-80	MERCK

INSTRUMENTS/ EQUIPMENTS**Table – 8:** List of equipments

S. No.	Equipments	Manufacturer
1.	UV Spectrophotometer	Shimadzu, Japan
2.	Dissolution Apparatus	Electro Labs
3.	Balance	Sartorius
4.	pH meter	Systronic, Ahmedabad
5.	Water Bath	Remi
6.	Magnetic Stirrer	Remi

METHODOLOGY:**Preparation of standard calibration curve of Trimethoprim:**

50mg of Trimethoprim was dissolved in little amount of ethanol in a 50ml of volumetric flask and the solution is made up of with water up to 50ml. The Standard Solution of Trimethoprim was subsequently diluted to obtain in a series of dilutions containing 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 µg of Trimethoprim in 1ml solution. The absorbances of these solutions were measured in UV spectrophotometer at 271nm using distilled water as blank.

Solubility study:

Equilibrium solubility of Trimethoprim was measured in various oils viz. castor oil, sunflower oil, oleic acid. An excess amount of Trimethoprim was added to each of selected vehicles and the mixture was stirred continuously for 72 hr at $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. After equilibrium was attained, the mixture was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 min, and the obtained supernatant was filtered through a membrane filter (Himedia) having pore size of 0.45µm. Absorbance of the filtrate was measured using a double beam UV/VIS spectrophotometer at λ_{max} of 271 nm. The content of Trimethoprim was determined using a previously constructed standard calibration curve.

Construction of pseudo-ternary phase diagram[82]

The pseudo-ternary phase diagrams were constructed by water titration method at room temperature. The ratios of surfactant and co-surfactant (Smix) were used 1:1, 2:1, 3:1 and 1:2. Tween 80 and PEG 400 were used as surfactant and co-surfactant and oleic acid was used as an oil phase. Mixtures of Smix and oil ratio from 9:1 to 1:9 were titrated by adding the water drop by drop. During the titration samples were stirred to allow equilibration and at the same time examined for the transparency. Samples with low viscosity, single phase and transparent nature were considered as stable SEDDS formulation. The data obtain after titration was used for the construction of pseudoternary phase diagram.

Preparation of SEDDS Formulations

A series of SMEDDS formulations were prepared using Tween 80 alone and Tween 80 and PEG 400 as the S/CoS combination and oleic acid as the oil (Table 9). In all the formulations, the level of trimethoprim was kept constant (i.e., 16.66% wt/wt of the total formulation weight). Briefly, accurately weighed trimethoprim was placed in a glass vial, and oil, surfactant, and cosurfactant were added. Then the components were mixed by gentle stirring and vortex mixing and were heated at 40°C on a magnetic stirrer, until trimethoprim was perfectly dissolved. The mixture was stored at room temperature until further use.

Table – 9: Formula for Preparation of SEDDS

Ingredients	Quality (mg)						
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7
Trimethoprim	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000
Oleic acid	500	1000	1500	2000	2500	1000	1500
Tween 80	4500	4000	3500	3000	2500	2000	1750
PEG-400	--	--	--	--	--	2000	1750

Figure – 4: Self emulsifying drug delivery systems of Trimethoprim**EVALUATION TEST:****Dispersibility Test**

The efficiency of self-emulsification of oral nano or micro emulsion is assessed by using a standard USP XXII dissolution apparatus 2 for dispersibility test.

One millilitre of each formulation was added in 500mL of water at 37 ± 1 °C. A standard stainless steel dissolution paddle is used with rotating speed of 50 rpm provided gentle agitation. The *in vitro* performance of the formulations is visually assessed using the following grading system:

Grade A: Rapidly forming (within 1 min) nanoemulsion, having a clear or bluish appearance.

Grade B: Rapidly forming, slightly less clear emulsion, having a bluish white appearance.

Grade C: Fine milky emulsion that formed within 2min

Grade D: Dull, greyish white emulsion having slightly oily appearance that is slow to emulsify (longer than 2min).

Grade E: Formulation, exhibiting either poor or minimal emulsification with large oil globules present on the surface.

Grade A and Grade B formulation will remain as nanoemulsion when dispersed in GIT. While formulation falling in Grade C could be recommend for SEDDS formulation. [83]

Droplet Size Analysis

The droplet size of the SEEDS is determined using a Zetasizer version 6.20 at Malven Instruments Ltd., Hyderabad. 1 mL of the formulation was diluted with water to 250 ml in a volumetric flask and gently mixed by inverting the flask. The droplet size distributions of the resultant emulsions were determined using Malvern Particle Size Analyzer (version 6.20 at Malven Instruments Ltd., Hyderabad). The values of mean emulsion droplet diameters (MEDD) were compared.

Effect of dilution on globule size:

In order to simulate *in vivo* dilution behaviour, effect of dilution volume by distilled water on droplet size was measured. Triplicate samples of selected pre-concentrates were diluted in different ratios like 1:50, 1:100 and 1:1000 and then the size was measured.

Scanning Electron Microscopy

SEDDS was diluted with distilled water 1:25 and mixed by slightly shaking. The morphology (Shape) of SMEDDS was observed by scanning electron microscope at Malven Instruments Ltd., Hyderabad.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**Standard curve for Trimethoprim****Figure – 6:** Solubility of Pioglitazone hydrochloride in various oils, surfactants co-solvents and water

Solubility studies were carried out to identify the oil, surfactant and co surfactant that possess good solubilization potential for Trimethoprim. Solubility of Trimethoprim in various oils is shown in figure – 5 and solubility of drug in surfactant and co- surfactant were observed to be 1.6 mg/mL in Tween 80 and 16.25 mg/mL in PEG 400. Oleic acid was selected as an oil phase for further studies due to its higher solubilization potential (12.3mg/mL) for Trimethoprim.

Pseudo ternary phase diagram study

From the above chosen oils, surfactant and co-solvents were taken in different ratios for the construction of ternary phase diagrams to know the

emulsion and micro-emulsion domains such that at particular concentration of oil, surfactant and co-solvent ratios, a stable self-emulsifying formulation is formed.

The Self emulsification process is affected on the concentration of Tween 80 and PEG 400 and their ratio. Micro emulsion region was appeared at surfactant concentration (20-65%) of W/W, co-solvent concentration at (20-60%). So the concentration of oil, surfactant and co-solvent was selected in these domains for the study. From the phase diagrams, it was observed that self emulsifying region increased with increasing concentrations of surfactant or combination of surfactant and co-

surfactant. Efficiency of self-emulsification was good when the surfactant concentration was increased

Vehicles selected for the formulation should have the ability to solubilize the drug extensively to obtain a concentrated form of the emulsions. Trimethoprim had higher solubility in PEG 400 than other vehicles. Pseudo-ternary phase diagrams were constructed to identify the efficient self-emulsifying region using oleic acid as oil, PEG 400 as co-solvent,

and Tween 80 as emulsifier. When the co-solvent is added to the system, it is able to dissolve the drug. However, when the content of PEG 400 is too high, the mixture form a gel mass upon addition of water. So, the content of co-solvent was determined to be between 0 and 50 percent. Isotropic mixtures can be formed when the content of surfactant is higher than 50 percent (Figure – 6).

Pseudo-ternary phase diagram

Figure – 7: Pseudo ternary diagram of surfactant and co surfactant in various ratios in oleic acid and water system

Figure – 6: Pseudo ternary diagram of surfactant and co surfactant in various ratios

The average size of droplets formed after emulsification was measured by using Malvern Zetasizer at 25°C, which was found to be 178.3 nm with poly dispersity index of 0.184 showing that the particles generated were mono disperse (Figure – 7). The formulations F7 showed no effect on dilution.

Scanning Electron Microscopy

Figure–9: Scanning electron microscopy of optimized formulations.
(a) Formulation F2. (b) Formulation F3. (c) & (d) Formulation F7.

The SEM study of the optimized emulsified formulation reveals that the formulation F7 producing stable spherical droplets of oleic acid dispersed uniformly. Formulations like F2 and F3 are producing matrix (gel) like structure as shown in figure 8 (a) and figure 8 (b) when dispersed in water. This matrix type structure may be attributed to the probable liquid crystalline structure which can be confirmed by further X-ray diffraction analysis.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

SEDDS formulations were successfully designed by constructing pseudo ternary diagrams and evaluated. Dissolution rate limited absorption of Trimethoprm was surmounted by producing droplets of nano size range, by which solubility and dissolution rate is, enhanced which in turn helps in improving the bioavailability. Trimethoprim SEDDS was developed

using oleic acid as lipid phase, Tween 80 as surfactant and PEG 400 as co surfactant. Droplet size was found to be in nanometer range (178.3 nm). Future research can be directed towards exploring the pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamics studies of such formulation. SEDDS can be explored for further dosage form design of drugs suffering from poor aqueous solubility or BCS class-II drugs.

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